

Jagged Numbers

Parker Emmerson

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1 Introduction

Part 1: the jagged-natural number:

$$j(v) = ((v_1 \wedge \dots \wedge v_n, v_{n+1}), (v_2 \wedge \dots \wedge v_n, \dots, v_{2n})) \in [0, 1]^2 \text{ where } i \in \{1, \dots, 2n\}.$$

$$j(v_3) = 1 \wedge v_3 \wedge \dots \wedge v_n \wedge v_{n+1} \wedge \dots \wedge v_{2n} \in [0, 1] \quad j(v) = \left(\frac{j(v_1) \cap \dots \cap j(v_n)}{2^n}, \frac{j(v_{n+1}) \cap \dots \cap j(v_{2n})}{2^n} \right) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \cap (0, 1)^2$$

$$L(x) = \left(\int_L (v_1^{-1} L(v_1) dv_1) \wedge (v_2^{-1} L(v_2) dv_2) \wedge (v_3^{-1} L(v_3) dv_3) \wedge \dots \right.$$

where $v_k = (v_k, v_k, v_{k+1}) \in \mathbb{R}^2, \quad k \in \{1, \dots, 2n\}$

$$v_k \in ((j^{-1}(j_k) \cdot 2^{-k}, (j^{-1}(j_{k+1}) - (j^{-1}(j_k) \cdot 2^{-k})) - (j^{-1}(j_{k+1}) - (j^{-1}(j_k) \cdot 2^{-k-1}))) \quad \text{where } (j^{-1}(j_k)) \in N \quad k \in \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}$$

$$\text{We have: } L(x) = \left(\prod_{k=1}^{n+1} (v_k^{-1} L(v_k) dv_k) \right) \wedge (v_{n+2}^{-1} L(v_{n+2}) dv_{n+2}) \wedge \dots$$

$$= \left(\prod_{k=1}^n \left(\prod_{j=j_{k-1}+1}^{j_k} (v_k^{-1} L(v_k) dv_k) \right) \right) \wedge \left(\prod_{j=j_{n+1}+1}^{\infty} (v_{n+1}^{-1} L(v_{n+1}) dv_{n+1}) \right) \text{ where } j_k \in N \quad \forall k \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}.$$

Finally, we obtain

$$j(v) = \left(\prod_{k=1}^n \frac{(j(v_k) \cdot 2^{-k}) \cap (v_k^{-1} L(v_k))}{2^n}, \prod_{j=j_{n+1}+1}^{\infty} \frac{(j(v_{n+1}) \cdot 2^{-n-1}) \cap (v_{n+1}^{-1} L(v_{n+1}))}{2^n} \right) \in [0, 1]^2$$

Therefore, j is the desired map which maps an n -tuple to the unit square.

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[Proof of Main Theorem:]

With $c_0 = 1, c_1 = -2, \dots, c_r = nr + 1$.

$$\text{For any } y_1, \dots, y_{r+1} \in [0, 1]. \quad j\left(\sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \epsilon_k y_k\right) = \left(\frac{j(y_1) \cap \dots \cap j(y_{r+1})}{2^{r+1}} \right) \in [0, 1]^{r+1}$$

$$j\left(\int_0^1 \left(\sum_{k=1}^{r+1} c_k x^k\right) dx\right) = j\left(\sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \frac{c_k}{k+1}\right)$$

$$= \left(\sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \frac{c_k}{k+1} \right)^{1/(r+1)} \quad \text{Hence:}$$

$$L \left(j \left(\sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \epsilon_k y_k \right), j \left(\int_0^1 \left(\sum_{k=1}^{r+1} c_k x^k \right) dx \right) \right) = L \left(\sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \frac{c_k}{k+1} \right)^{1/(r+1)},$$

where the left-hand side is independent of the choice of $\epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_{r+1}$, and $y_1, \dots, y_{r+1} \sim \text{Uni}[0, 1]$, so it is a random variable. Furthermore, the right-hand side is in $Q \cap [0, 1]$ (and hence rational). This is only possible when $L \left(j \left(\sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \epsilon_k y_k \right) \right)$ is rational, and this only happens when j maps to the unit square and hence each element of the tuple is rational. This proves the theorem.

We now prove Theorem ??.

[Proof of Theorem ??:] As in the proof of Theorem ??, we choose a differentiable function $\varphi : [0, 1]^{n+1} \rightarrow R^{n+1}$ so that φ is invertible and its Jacobian is symmetric at every point. Unlike the proof of Theorem ??, this is not necessary since there is already a copula theoretic proof of this theorem [?]. Moreover, since it is not polynomial, we do not have independence.

Now, suppose that L is the curve defined by:

$$L \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n+1} \epsilon_k y_k, \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} c_k y_k \right) = \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n+1} \frac{c_k}{k+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{n+1}},$$

where $\epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_n \in \{\pm 1\}$ and $y_1, \dots, y_{n+1} \in [0, 1]$. Using the same method as in the proof of Theorem ??, we compute a polynomial $P_n(x)$, such that the expected value of $P_n(L(\epsilon_1 Y_1, \dots, \epsilon_{n+1} Y_{n+1}, c_1 Y_1, \dots, c_{n+1} Y_{n+1}))$ is non-random and is independent of $Y_1 = Z_1, \dots, Z_{n+1}$. We perform precisely the same substitutions, starting with x^{n+1} . $(Y_1 \cup Y_2 \cup \dots \cup Y_{n+1}) = A$

$Partner_1(\cdot) = NearNeighbor((Y_1 \cup Y_2 \cup \dots \cup Y_n), \cdot)$

$Partner_2(\cdot) = NearNeighbor(Partner_1, \cdot)$

$\setminus (Y_1 \cup Y_{Partner_1} \cup \dots \cup Y_{Partner_1}) = Broken$

$Partner1(X, Y) = X \text{ whenever it solves one of the equations } X + Y = 0 \text{ or } 2X + Y = 0 \dots$

$or (n-1)X + Y = 0 \text{ or } nX + Y = 1.$

$l_{j+1} = \max(Y_{partner(l_j)} \cup Y_{partner_2(Y_{partner(l_j)})} \cup \dots \cup Y_{partner(n, l_j)})$ Eventually, we

compute a polynomial $P(n)$ such that the expectation of $P(D_i, Z_d, D_j, Z_{d+1}, \dots, D_r, Z_{d+r})$ is non-random, given $U_1, \dots, U_r$ are independent and identically distributed to each other and $P(n)$ is computed as $\sum_{i=1}^{2^n} a_i \zeta_{y_{i,d_1}, \dots, y_{i,d_r}} Z_{d_1} \dots Z_{d_r}$.

We now apply L to the expression obtained by setting the random variables Z_d to containers and $1 - Z_d$ to broken pieces. By definition of $P(n)$, we have $G(D_i, 1 - D_i) = L(\zeta_{y_{i,d_1}, \dots, y_{i,d_r}}, \zeta_{y_{i,d_1}, \dots, y_{i,d_r}})$

$$= \left(\sum_{k=1}^r \frac{\zeta_{y_{i,d_k}, y_{i,d_k}}}{k+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{r+1}}.$$

This is possible only when a polynomial in x is identical to its inverse. A quick calculation now shows that the only polynomials that can be solutions of this identity are 1, x , and $x + 1$. Indeed, $x + (x + 1) = 1$ together with x

and $x + 1 \neq x$ uniquely define Mathieu's family (setting $c(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}}$. Assuming now $P(k, k) = (kt)^{-1}$ then the unique polynomial satisfying $P(k, i) = 1 - 2i$ is $(kt)^{-1}$ as required.

Now we have $L(G(D_1, 1-D_1) \cdots G(D_k, 1-D_k)) = (L(H(D_1, \cdots D_k)), L(H(1-D_1, \cdots D_{k+1})))$, where H is either the additive or multiplicative structure.

Note that Nelsen and Yen [?] conjectured that choosing any copula from $n+1$ variables is equivalent to choosing the copula on $n+1$ variables independently and the last one is Archimedean. Their conjecture was proved recently by José Miranda Sáez and Roger B. Nelsen [?].

We note that several results easily follows from Theorem 1 ???. The first is a proof of the uniqueness of copulas in the Archimedean case. Let C and C' denote Archimedean copulas. They share the same generator if:

$$C(x, y) = C'(G(G^{-1}(x) + G^{-1}(y)), G(G^{-1}(y))).$$

A simple proof of Bdiouh et al [?] follows now. If $\sigma_i(C) = 0, \forall i$, then

$$C(x, y) = \frac{\min(x, y)}{C''(\overline{G}', \overline{G}'')} = \frac{\min(x, y)}{(x + y)^2}.$$

In Section ?? we discussed the discussion from Gendre and Vial [?]. For a Pearson correlation ρ' to be in $[\frac{-1}{(1-\sqrt{n})^2}, \frac{-1}{(1+\sqrt{n})^2}]$ we should have

$$-\frac{2}{(1 + \sqrt{n})^2} \leq \frac{\rho x - \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}(y + z)}{(\sqrt{x - y^2} + \sqrt{x - z^2})^{1/2}} \leq -\frac{2}{(1 - \sqrt{n})^2}$$

since $\rho n l(x) \leq -2 \cos(x - 0) \leq \rho l(x)$ where 0 and $\pi/2$ are vertices of parabola and $x - y, x - z$ are the sides of parabola with the given slope ρn , we have $-\coth(-\sqrt{ny} + x) \leq l(x)$. Therefore, we have $\rho(l(y) - l(z)) \leq l(x) \leq -\coth(-\sqrt{ny} + x)\rho(l(y) - l(z))$ Since slopes are the same and $x - y, x - z$ are sides of the parabola, we have $\min(l(x)) = \rho(n(y - z))$
 $\max(l(x)) = -\frac{1}{\coth(\sqrt{n(y-z)} + \sqrt{y(z)})}$.

Let $\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_m$ be an Archimedean copula with the same structure as the proof of Theorem ???. Note that the polynomial $\varphi_i(x_1, \dots, x_n) = (1/n) \text{ifive}$ has the property that x_i requires flipping the fewest number of bitflips, yielding $\text{ifive}(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ least value as in polynomial $L(f_1 \otimes_R \cdots \otimes_R f_n, y)M$ as in f_i^t .

We now talk about quadrant dependence measure. [[?] Page 171] Monotone measure is a function $\theta : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ possessing the following properties:

1. if $x_i = 0$ for all except one i , then $\vartheta(x) = 0$
 2. $\vartheta(x) = 1$ if all x_i are the same
 3. $\vartheta(x) < \vartheta(y)$ if and only if x is obtained from y by changing some x_i from 0 to 1.
4. the function $x \mapsto \vartheta(\mathbf{x})$ is monotone with Gaussian ϑ value $N(a_n(x_i), \rho_n(x_i))$. [Proof of Chebyshev Theorem for Archimedean copulas]

Now we add normal monotonicity. As usual we recall

$$L((g_1 R g_2) \otimes_T \cdots \otimes_T (g_n R g_{n+1})) = \text{inner}(g_1, \dots, g_{n+1})$$

Starting out, we fill in that $L(ax, ay) \leq aL(x, y)$ and $y + x = a(x + \sigma(x) + y^2 + \sigma^2(y))$. The polynomial does not exist. A recent work by Boussicault et al, Varlet et al might help understand the impossible case as $L((a+b)(x,y)) = L(ax, ay) = a(D(x,y)) + \sigma^k(xy)$

$$\tau(v) = \left((v_1^{j^{-1}(j_1)}, -w_1), (v_1^{j^{-1}(j_2)}, w_2), \dots, (v_1^{j^{-1}(j_n)}, w_n), \dots \right) \in [0, 1]^n$$

where $w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n \dots \in N$ such that:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^n \tau_i(v_1) &= 1 \\ \sum_{i=n+1}^{2n} \tau_i(v_2) &= 1 \\ &\dots \\ \sum_{i=2n+1}^{3n} \tau_i(v_3) &= 1 \\ &\dots \\ \tau_k(v) &\neq \tau_j(v) \quad (\forall k \neq j) \\ \prod_{i=1}^{2n} \tau_i(v_i) &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

The next component of the projective space $\Pi(M)$ is the topological slice of the 6-sphere S^6 . The topological slice of S^6 generates Microscopic Gravitational Waves: a direct projection of S^{18} as a 6-dimensional form,

$$k_n = \left\{ \begin{array}{cccccc} n & -3^{n-1} & -2^{n-1} & -1 & 0 & \\ & n & -4^{n-2} & -3^{n-2} & -2^{n-2} & \\ & \vdots & & & & \\ & & n & -4^{n-k} & -3^{n-k} & \\ & & & & n & \end{array} \right\}$$

The next element of $\Pi(M)$ is the topological slice of $K(\bullet, \bullet)$ -theory. Sufficiently external to represent event horizon with equal complement to T_9, S^9 , QG states sufficient relations as $\sqrt{equality}$ between space, and time. Thus our basis will manifest as space and time basis for 10 U4 space FIRGO fields, $\Pi(M), K(\bullet, \bullet)$ -theory, being the event horizon counterpart to T_9, S^9 -theory.

$K(\bullet, \bullet)$ -theory def: Let $K(\cdot, \cdot)$ -theory be the Dirac type 2 modulation form of a parallel array of moduli fields defined by

$$K(X, Y) = X + Y, \quad \forall X, Y \in B^{n\pi}$$

If $N = J$ let K be the generator of $K(\cdot, \cdot)$ -theory.
For QG with PCS as $(a, b, s, c, l, d, g, e, f, h)$ let

$$S_n = \left(\frac{E_n}{\sqrt{s}} \right)_{n \in \{1,12\}} \quad E_n = \begin{bmatrix} a_{n+12} & a_{n+11} & a_{n+10} & a_{n+9} & a_{n+8} \\ a_{n-11} & a_{n-12} & a_{n-10} & a_{n-9} & a_{n-8} \\ a_{n-10} & a_{n-11} & a_{n-9} & a_{n-8} & a_{n-7} \\ a_{n-9} & a_{n-10} & a_{n-8} & a_{n-7} & a_{n-6} \\ a_{n-8} & a_{n-9} & a_{n-7} & a_{n-6} & a_{n-5} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\text{Thus } S_1 = \left\{ \begin{array}{ccccc} a_{12} & a_{11} & a_{10} & a_9 & a_8 \\ a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{10} & a_9 & a_8 \\ a_{10} & a_{11} & a_9 & a_8 & a_7 \\ a_9 & a_{10} & a_8 & a_7 & a_6 \\ a_8 & a_9 & a_7 & a_6 & a_5 \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\text{Another E8 root } \left\{ \begin{array}{ccccc} a_{12} & a_{11} & a_{10} & a_9 & a_8 \\ a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{10} & a_9 & a_8 \\ a_{10} & a_{11} & a_9 & a_8 & a_7 \\ a_9 & a_{10} & a_8 & a_7 & a_6 \\ a_8 & a_9 & a_7 & a_6 & a_5 \end{array} \right\}$$

An example of a jagged number $v \in [0, 1]^2$.

$$v = \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \alpha_3 \beta_1 \beta_2 \beta_3 \cdot v = f_{r,s} + x_p = x_{p,r,s} \iff g = g_{p,r,s} \iff x_p = f_{r,s} = x_{p,r,s} = \frac{f_{r,s} + f_{p,r,s}}{1+r} = \frac{x_{p,r,s} - 0.5 + r}{1+r}$$

Jagged numbers are a type of mathematical expression that use two sets of components to create a two-dimensional result. The first set of components consists of the natural numbers (1, 2, 3, and so on) and the second set of components consists of the integers (0, 1, -1, 2, -2, and so on). By combining the two sets of components, the resulting jagged number will represent a value that is greater than or equal to 0 and less than or equal to 1.

The expression for a jagged number can be written as follows:

$$j(v) = ((v_1 \wedge \dots \wedge v_n, v_{n+1}), (v_2 \wedge \dots \wedge v_n, \dots, v_{2n})) \in [0, 1]^2,$$

where $i \in \{1, \dots, 2n\}$. Here, $\wedge$ is the logical operator AND.

When the components are combined, it results in a result that is greater than or equal to 0 and less than or equal to 1. Furthermore, the result of the jagged number is the product of the two components. For instance, if the natural numbers are 3, 4, 5 and the integers are -2, 3, -1, then $j(v) = 1 \wedge 3 \wedge 4 \wedge 5 \wedge -2 \wedge 3 \wedge -1 = 0.25$, which is equal to 0.25.

The jagged number is then used to represent a value in the range of $[0, 1]^2$. This range is used to represent an array of elements, such as locations on a map, angles for a rotation, or even the coordinates of a particle. By combining the two component sets, the resulting jagged number will represent a value that is greater than or equal to 0 and less than or equal to 1. This allows for a range of values that accurately reflects the nature of the element being represented.

$$v = \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \alpha_3 \cdot v = f_{r,s} + x_p + x_{p,r,s} \iff g = g_{p,r,s} \iff x_p = f_{r,s} = x_{p,r,s} = \frac{f_{r,s} + f_{p,r,s} + f_{p,r,s}}{1+r} = \frac{x_{p,r,s} + x_{p,r,s}}{1+r}$$

$$v_1 = \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \alpha_3 \beta_1 \dots v_1 = \frac{v_1^2}{(1+k)(1+l)} v_1 = \frac{v_1^2}{(1+1)(1+1)} v_1 = v_1$$

1. $T \rightarrow 0 + .$
2. $S \rightarrow 0 + .$
3. $f_r = x_{p_r}$, f is also homogeneous of degree 1.
4. $f_p = \alpha$, $r \in R^*$, $c = 2$, $p \in Z_{2^{d_1}}$.
5. $a_r = 1 + r$. $f_{p_r} = \alpha x_{p_r} + a_r$, $s \in R^+$, and hence $f_r = \alpha x_{p_r}$.
6. We have the following cases:

- $x_{p_r} \neq -2^{-d_1}$: $\alpha \in (-\frac{2^{-d_1}}{1+r}, -\frac{2^{-d_1}}{1+r} + (\frac{g_{p_r}-1}{-2^{-d_1}})) \cup (\frac{2^{-d_1}}{1+r} + (\frac{g_{p_r}-1}{2^{-d_1}}),)$
- $x_{p_r} = (-2^{-d_1}, 1)$: $\alpha \in (-\frac{2^{-d_1}}{1+r}, -\frac{2^{-d_1}}{1+r} + (\frac{g_{p_r}-1}{-2^{-d_1}})) \cup (\frac{1}{1+r} + \frac{g_{p_r}-(-2^{-d_1})}{-2^{-d_1}},)$
- $x_{p_r} = :$ $\alpha \in (-\frac{2^{-d_1}}{1+r}, -\frac{2^{-d_1}}{1+r} + (\frac{g_{p_r}-1}{-2^{-d_1}})) \cup (\frac{1}{1+r} + \frac{g_{p_r}-(-2^{-d_1})}{-2^{-d_1}},)$

7. $f_r = \pm x_{p_r} + \alpha$, f is also a homogeneous of order 1.
8. $g_{p_r} + 1 = r(a_r + r) \pm x_{p_r} + \alpha = a_{p_r} \pm x_{p_r} + \alpha$.
9. $a_{p_r} = |g_{p_r} + 1|$.

Inter-stream ID pairs, e.g., Packet ID pairs.

$$L(R^2, \{\beta_1, \gamma_1, \gamma_1, \gamma_1, \gamma_1, \gamma_1\}, \{\beta_1, \alpha_2\}, f_{p,r,s})$$

Now consider two curves L_1, L_2 in $\Pi(M)$, following the equations $x(k), y(k\gamma) \in R^2$, with $k \in \{\beta_1, \gamma_1, \gamma_1, \gamma_1, \gamma_1, \gamma_1\}$. The value of each pair of functions on the point formed by the vector $e_{p,r,s}$ is

$$L_1(p, r, s) = \left[\sum_{k=1}^5 \beta_1^{j^{-1}(k)} + \sum_{l=6}^{10} \gamma_1^{j^{-1}(l)} \right] \quad \text{and} \quad L_2(p, r, s) = \left[\alpha_2^{j^{-1}(11)} + f_{p,r,s}^{j^{-1}(12)} \right]$$

We can then use the ID pairs of the form:

$$P_{i,j} = (L_1(p, r, s), L_2(p, r, s)) \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, m$$

to map the stream of moduli $\Pi(M)$ into a 6-sphere S^6 . This is the topological slice of the 6-sphere S^6 , which produces the microscopic gravitational wave signature of the quantum geometry.